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“THE CEO”

As soon as Linda got out of the car, people started whispering to each other. Linda knew what this is all about, but she just ignored it. She is focused with the company's welfare, not with the rumors surrounding it. Linda is a charismatic woman in her thirties. She is a new name in the company, no one knows her background or where she came from. What makes her more intriguing is the fact that she entered the company without proper screening, even naming herself as our new Chief Executive Officer. My co-workers call her the “great Enoki”. An Enoki is a type of an edible mushroom. Linda is that “mushroom”, and “Enoki” because Enoki mushrooms are wild mushrooms. In short, Linda is that wild mushroom that sprouted out in the company mysteriously, not to mention wildly. Which also led us to wonder, “Where could our Chief Executive Officer be?”

A janitress whispered, “I heard that she poisoned our former CEO in order to have such position in the company.”

Another janitress replied, “I heard it, all right. But how did she do it? Was she close to him?”

Our former CEO, Mr. Emmanuel Kang announced his hiatus from the company, one day before Linda came in. Everything happened so quickly, I couldn't blame people for judging because it is very clear that our former CEO's hiatus, has something to do with Linda's sudden arrival in the company. Nevertheless, Linda did not mind the coldness of the people in the company. She can read every raised eyebrow, every harsh tone, and every silence. Nobody respected her, but she did her job anyway! When stocks came tumbling down, Linda always has a way of solving it, which keeps the company thriving, stocks skyrocketing up to this very moment. The moment she entered the company, she has proven her credibility a thousand times already, but none of it seemed to matter, she remained the “great Enoki” in the eyes of many.

So, to ease my curiosity, I ran a few background check on our dear Linda. At first, I had so much trouble looking up for information about her because she has zero social media presence. Her name, Linda Lee itself, doesn't make any sense! So, I decided to plant a tracker on Linda's car and the truth blew my mind.

It was Friday evening, Linda casually went out of her office and headed to her home, which I only happened to find out because of the tracker that I planted in her car. She lived in a shabby home down the suburbs. I went there discreetly the following day only to witness that she was not alone after all. With her, is a man in his fifties, sitting in a wheel chair, thin and weak, unable to speak but still responsive. Seeing that made me tremble in fear because when I sneaked behind the bushes, I couldn't believe what my eyes have seen. It was our former CEO, sitting in that wheel chair, and Linda is with him.

Scenes started flashing in my mind like movies in a cinema but I decided to keep calm and think rationally. “I need to talk to her,” I said to myself, “I need to clear things out. She has to clear her name out, right? She deserves a benefit

of the doubt.” So, I stood up from the bushes, Linda almost got up from her chair upon seeing me, while Mr. Kang’s eyes grew wide.

I opened my mouth and spilled blatantly, “Mr. Kang, Miss Linda, I know my presence here in your private residence shocked you, but I am here in order to clarify things because I couldn’t afford to work in a company where various rumors spread here and there about or CEO.”

I thought Linda would be mad but no, she was surprisingly calm and poised. “Come in,” she said, “let’s talk it out after I bring my father to his room. You see, he needs plenty of rest.”

I nodded, unable to utter a single word, but my mind was literally blowing. “Mr. Kang is Linda’s father? Why didn’t I think of that?”

When Linda came out from Mr. Kang’s room, she offered me a cup of coffee and then, we started talking and things began to unfold. Linda is Mr. Kang’s only daughter, her mom died when she was still very young, and she grew up in this little home in the suburb where her mom lived before God called her home. Linda lived here ever since because she doesn’t want to be separated from her mother’s memories, she even changed her surname from Kang to Lee, after her mother. Growing up, she tried so hard to disassociate herself with her father’s name, but now that her father is ill, she felt the need to step up for the company while preserving her peace in this shabby home. The Linda that I see in the company is smart, stern, and intimidating but this Linda that I am facing is calm, poised, and gentle. Surely, we should not read a book by its cover.

I asked her if she felt the coldness of the people in the company. Her reply was obviously, “Yes.” But she chose not to respond harshly, instead, she responded calmly, quietly, and wisely. As the current CEO, she made sure that she is sharp to read every room yet gentle to respond to every worker. At first, I honestly couldn’t understand why she did this when she can choose to talk back and tell everyone the truth. However, later that day, I went home happy and in peace, knowing that all of the rumors circulating in the company are merely false accusations and misconceptions. As I drove myself home, Linda’s words lingered in my mind. “You do not need to explain yourself to everyone because no matter how hard you try to be good, people will always have something to say about you. People’s opinions always go out of hand. You wouldn’t be liked by everyone but you can always choose to be kind to everyone. At the end of the day, everything will rely on how you responded to false accusations and rumors.”

Response always matters, and as for her, she chose to respond calmly, quietly, and wisely. After all, she was not concerned with the money that she may gain from the company, but with the welfare of the people who are part of and rely with the company. When people whispered in front of her, she was aware, but she smiled at them anyway. When people disrespected her, she got the message, but she chose to respect them anyway. Then I realized, “Ah, that is the reason why nobody could afford to drag her down. She remained good while the others were judging her. She showed everyone that she was aware with all the rumors circulating in the company, but she showed everyone that she doesn’t owe anyone an explanation. She knows herself. She is a good person, she doesn’t have to prove herself to anybody. As long as she knows she is not hurting anybody, she is willing to do her job to the best of her ability.”

The following week, I went to the office. Day by day, I observed how my co-workers would react in Miss Linda’s presence. As the time went by, things began to unfold, people began to open up their minds. Miss Linda did the usual, smile, response with respect, and now I see her love for the company and every one of us here. The people who were once whispering rumors about her stopped, and soon, the atmosphere turned as it used to be. Miss Linda is right. When conflicts, circumstances, unavoidable matters and issues emerge, our response always matters, and may we always choose to respond to these situations calmly, quietly, and wisely. Because in every problem and in every conflict, the truth and the good will always prevail. All conflicts will be resolved and problems will be solved if we learn to act to it rationally, wisely, and truthfully.

